

Effect of foliar sprays on brown planthopper (BPH) population and damage in upland rice (variety Kinanda).^a IRRI, 1976 wet season.

Insecticide ^b	BPH population (no./10 linear-m row) 94 DS ^c	Resurgence ratio (x:1) ^d	Hopperburn (%) 117 DS
Decamethrin	6,733 a	16.4	100
Methyl parathion	2,468 a	6.0	75
Diazinon	1,919 ab	4.1	55
BPMC	178 c	0.4	1
Perthane	29 d	0.1	0
Control	411 bc	—	4

^a In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^b Insecticides were applied three times at 49, 72, and 94 days after seeding (DS) at 0.75 kg a.i./ha.

^c The planthopper counts at 94 DS were made before the third application.

^d Resurgence ratio = $\frac{\text{number of brown planthoppers in insecticide treatment}}{\text{number of brown planthoppers in untreated control}}$

Field plot layout used in the field evaluation of rice for brown planthopper resistance IRRI, 1978.

active ingredient/ha. The spray is directed at the canopy. Plants are sprayed at 10-day intervals beginning at 30 days after transplanting. Plant damage is first rated when the adjacent susceptible check variety is killed, then is rated at 1-week intervals until increase in damage ceases. The extent of damage as based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice and

the percentage of hopperburned plants are then recorded. For additional information on BPH buildup, insects are counted at regular intervals throughout the crop season. Varieties with moderate levels of field resistance are easier to detect with this technique than with the greenhouse method. *WY*

Varietal resistance to striped rice borer *Chilo suppressalis*

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One hundred and twenty-seven rice varieties and lines were evaluated to determine the correlation among percentage of infested tillers, larval

number, and larval weight.

Twenty days after seeding, plants were transplanted in two replications of six hills (2 plants/hill) in a net house. Thirty 10- × 12-cm dishes containing 200 larvae on straw were placed in the middle of the net house so that moths could emerge and infest the varieties.

After 50 days, all stems of each rice were dissected, the larvae and infested tillers were counted, and larval weights were determined.

The percentage of infested tillers correlated positively with both the number of larvae and the larval weights in all rices (Fig. 1, 2).

In varieties with a low number of infested tillers, there was a high correlation between infested tillers and number of larvae, but in varieties with high infestation (more than 80%), number of infested tillers did not correlate significantly with number of larvae.

In moderately resistant varieties (less than 80% infested tillers), the percentage of infested tillers correlated significantly with larval weights. As larval numbers increased, larval lengths and body weights were reduced proportionately. The resistant check IR747 had 51% tiller infestation, but the larvae that fed on it had significantly lower body weights and numbers. *WY*

1. Relationship between percentage of infested tillers and number of striped rice borers in rices evaluated in the screenhouse. Suweon, Korea.

2. Relationship between percentage of infested tillers and larval weight of striped rice borers in rices evaluated in the screenhouse. Suweon, Korea.